

Exploring error patterns in English writing: a pathway to innovative multimodal instructional material

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ABSTRACT

Considered as a crucial element that leads to better academic performance, Filipino learners always aim to master English language skills. Among various factors that affect the learning of English language skills, the availability of resources that cater to a diverse set of learners is important. Using semiotic or multimodal resources may help teachers assist students in enhancing their macro skills in the English language. This developmental research aimed to design, develop and evaluate a multimodal instructional material (IM) based on students identified common errors in writing. English major education students were selected as participants as they are important role-players in enhancing the future generation of learners in the English language. There were 39 freshman bachelor of secondary education (BSEd) English major students, three English teachers, two curriculum experts, and one information technology expert participated in the study. A panel of experts validated the instruments, which included the questionnaire to gauge the respondents' writing skills, the adapted rubric for writing proficiency, and the adapted evaluation form for printed IM exclusively used by the university. Results of the study revealed that the respondents' writing skills were poor. The evaluation conclusively showed that the IM was very acceptable for classroom use and teaching. It was recommended that the developed multimodal IM be used as a supplementary workbook to facilitate the need for primary English textbooks for the freshman BSEd English major students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Language proficiency is undeniably important to society in today's information age. One's ability to communicate effectively is commonly required in the business world making educators become embroiled in developing communication skills in school to convey intent and ensure accuracy. In the English language, the macro skills taught and practiced include listening, speaking, reading, and writing [1]. Among these macro skills, speaking and writing are often considered the hardest skills to develop because both requires constant practice. Hence, they are deemed as output skills. Several factors, personal and otherwise, have influenced learners' ability to express themselves clearly and effectively in either speech or writing. In a study that looks into language anxiety among English language learners in higher education [2], the majority of the interviewed learners report that they are very nervous when speaking in English and that they face great difficulty expressing themselves in English [3]. Learners have limited critical ability to respond appropriately

to an academic text [4] and they can also be aware of the essentialities of academic writing, yet they find difficulty in mastering or developing these skills [5].

Language curriculums in the Philippines substantially influence students' placement in overall classroom performance and achievement in examinations. This is because core subjects like mathematics and science are studied and taught in English. It is easier to facilitate comprehension among students if they can easily grasp concepts and topics in a language that they master and know very well. Common issues that Filipino learners encounter in studying the English language include limited exposure to the language outside the classroom, the inevitable reliance on and use of dialects at home, and insufficient practice in speaking and writing [6]. Lack of opportunities for meaningful communication in English often leads to feelings of anxiety and a decrease in language confidence [7]. Furthermore, traditional teaching methodologies often fail to engage students, resulting in failure to achieve outcomes.

Oftentimes, technology is tapped to help alleviate the problem. However, enhancing communication skills through technology is a tasking goal, too. Studies show that most students find technology-enhanced learning engaging, which facilitates English practice outside the classroom, and AI-powered tools are praised for boosting motivation and proficiency compared to traditional methods [8], it is crucially important to design and implement a pedagogically valid curriculum, one that is specific to the goals of a program. In the Philippines, the classroom has become the solid ground for meaningful interaction. Meanwhile, English language proficiency is considered crucial for academic performance and success. The study of Mendoza [9] concludes that students' English language proficiency could predict student's academic performance in science, mathematics, and English. This is because the medium of instruction used in teaching the said subjects is English. Thus, English language programs in school should be given attention. However, students encounter many challenges in writing in English. For example, many English teachers tend to stick to the traditional rote learning strategy which only limits opportunities for students to engage in meaningful writing activities in the classroom supposedly aimed to help them establish their personal writing style [10].

Towards the latter part of the 21st century, the Philippine educational system may have reached its turning point, as it seeks to address concerns with the development of linguistic abilities among Filipino students, and the reinforcement of their academic achievements on the other. As such, the country's traditional edge in English language proficiency is slowly being challenged by non-English-speaking Asian countries [11]. In line with these issues, further reformation of the country's English language education (ELE) is expected soon, because it may address the need for alignment of the overall goal, standards, and assessment of the program. Amidst all these, it is also equally important to discuss concerns in the English language programs in the context of other areas of study, specifically in the Philippine setting.

Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum No. 20, series of 2013, Article 1 cites that the New General Education (GE) curriculum for all undergraduate students regardless of their major aims to "expose them to various domains of knowledge and ways of comprehending social and natural realities, developing in the process intellectual competencies such as critical, analytical and creative thinking, and multiple forms of expression..." (p. 2). To support CHED Memorandum No. 20, CHED likewise underscored in CHED Memorandum No. 69, series of 2017, the importance of the GE faculty training for new general education core courses, and the objective was to develop educators' intellectual competencies. The training focused on the pedagogy and interdisciplinarity of the new GE courses.

Meanwhile, graduates of teacher education programs are expected to be effective oral and written communicators [12]. Proficiency in oral and written communication must be underscored in developing future teachers who play an integral role in developing learners' skills and attitudes in the 21st century. This is just one of the eight program outcomes outlined in the curriculum of the bachelor of secondary education (BSEd) major in English at the West Visayas State University (WVSU). Specific to this discipline is the goal of using technology in facilitating language learning and teaching, which necessitates the integration of multimodal context in the teaching and learning process.

Meanwhile, among the external campuses of WVSU, pre-service teachers are encouraged to use technology during classroom instruction to facilitate lecture discussions and other dynamic activities. The use of multimedia tools and equipment is integrated into the teaching profession, and much so in students' activities, assignments, and other co-curricular activities. However, it is quite obvious that in the preparation of instructional materials (IM), manuals, or modules, there has been minimal effort to introduce a multimodal approach in the context of instruction as there is much focus on the presentation of textual information during lecture discussions or even in individual or group reporting.

On this premise, it becomes a significant obligation of colleges and universities to prepare students on how to live and participate in the 21st century literate ways of behaving and doing things. As the youth are challenged to connect and enthusiastically use English in an ICT-saturated world, it behooves educators to focus on multi-literacy and skills upgrading to prepare them to meet the demands of time. For student

learning to occur substantially, it has to go beyond the four walls of the classroom across home, school, and local communities where conventional teaching may not be the common ground for true education.

According to Hamad *et al.* [3], a language curriculum that advances inclusive, learning-by-doing experiences would encourage more meaningful learning. An improved English language curriculum that operates on reflective learning pedagogy would motivate learners to become independent and critical language learners in line with the current trends in language learning. Unfortunately, answering reading comprehension questions and essay writing with limited listening and speaking exercises mainly characterizes traditional classroom practices. One way to enhance English language programs is the intensive analysis of students' English language skills by studying the errors that they commonly make in the classroom, or while studying the language. Doing this can highlight students' weaknesses in writing, particularly in the fields of spelling, grammar, sentence structure, and punctuation, among many others [13]. Considering these weaknesses and errors, previous studies have reported few methods or ways to mitigate writing errors through relevant activities such as graphic organizer strategies [14], peer assessment [15], and technology-assisted learning [16]. These findings relate to the importance of a need-specific integration of multimodal instructional tools or strategies in the teaching-learning process. In the context of this study, multimodal IM may be described as learning materials that use various semiotic modes (e.g., text, images, audio, and video) to deliver content and facilitate understanding among students [17].

A better understanding of either speech or writing errors may contribute to teaching effectiveness while focusing on multimodality in developing learners' skills and attitudes in the 21st century. Hence, this study is particularly directed towards finding out and analyzing students' errors in writing to develop an English multimodal IM that appropriately addresses the gap in their writing skills. However, this study is only limited to the development and evaluation of IM based on students' common writing errors. With this in mind, this study is focused on answering the following research questions:

- What are the common writing errors of the freshman BSEd English major students?
- What IM can be developed and what are its features to address the common writing errors of the freshman BSEd English major students?
- What is the level of acceptability of the IM as to objectives; physical aspects; activities; accuracy and up-to-datedness of information; and assessment as evaluated by the panel of experts?

2. METHOD

This study employed a developmental research design to understand common writing errors among BSEd students. Developmental research in IM development denotes a systematic approach encompassing the design, development, and evaluation of educational programs, processes, and products to ascertain their adherence to defined standards of internal consistency and efficacy [18]. Moreover, it is described as the study of the instructional design, development, and evaluation process as a whole or in terms of its particular process components [19]. It can study specific instructional design efforts or evaluate broader processes and tools. This study followed the input, process, and output (IPO) model and utilized the type I developmental research design. The IPO model is a framework used to analyze and optimize the educational system by categorizing its main components into three distinct stages: input, process, and output. Developmental research design is categorized into two types: type I and type II. Considering the objectives of this paper, the type I developmental research design is utilized. The type I developmental research design is where the product development process is used in a particular situation described and analyzed, and the final product is evaluated. Similarly, this paper presents the design and development of a multimodal IM and its evaluation based on a set of criteria. Furthermore, the study focused on creating and assessing multimodal IM in English to enhance the writing skills of BSEd English students or pre-service English teachers.

2.1. Respondents

The respondents of this study were 39 out of 43 first-year BSEd English major students who were taking the subject ELE 202-structure of English during the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023. This sample size was obtained with the use of Cochran formula assuming a 95% confidence level. The respondents were asked to answer the questionnaires for writing proficiency before designing and developing the IM. Students' responses to the questionnaires were utilized as baseline inputs to the development of a multimodal IM for ELE. Records from the Office of the Registrar of the university shows that there are 43 officially enrolled first-year BSEd students majoring in English. From this population, respondents were chosen through random sampling using the fishbowl technique.

2.2. Evaluators

Faculty members teaching the ELE 202 subject, English faculty, and curriculum experts validated the English IM. They also served as evaluators of the efficiency and usability of the said IM. Moreover, three English faculty from the school of teacher education were also asked to serve as evaluators. These faculty were purposively chosen based on their expertise in teaching different subjects in English. Their comments and suggestions about the IM were considered as they are essential in the iterative process of the design as well as in the development and improvement of the IM.

2.3. Ethical consideration

The conduct of this study was guided by the rules and code of ethics based on the standards of the American Psychological Association [20]. That is, this study must “do no harm” to the respondents. Furthermore, ethical guidelines such as privacy and confidentiality in conducting ethical research were observed. To do this, the researcher saw to it that respondents were briefed first as to the nature of the study during the orientation meeting before the conduct of the study so that matters about personal protection, privacy, and confidentiality are considerably well discussed. The following ethical principles were observed by the researcher in the conduct of the study: i) Request for permission to conduct the study from the campus administrator and school director; ii) Solicitation of informed consent form from the respondents before the conduct of the study for willingness and volunteerism; and iii) Adherence to strict confidentiality and respondents’ anonymity.

2.4. Data gathering instruments

The instruments used in the development of IM based on the common writing errors of freshman BSEd English major students are as:

- i) Questionnaire for writing assessment: to gauge understanding of students’ writing errors, a researcher-made questionnaire was made adapting details from that of Nghikembua [21]. The questionnaire is composed of two sections, namely: i) Section A, respondent’s profile and ii) Section b, essay writing activity using pictures as tools for writing. Picture talk will be the respondents’ writing activity. In picture talk, students are tasked to write about the pictures or drawings presented to them by the researcher. Respondents were asked to construct an essay (only one) based on their experiences through the given pictures. Writing errors were identified using a matrix. These errors are coded and they were identified according to sources and classification. For this study, the researcher identified errors based on a multimodal context for easy understanding of such errors committed by the respondents with emphasis on the two types of writing errors: interlingual and intralingual.
- ii) Instructional material evaluation form (IMEF): the IMEF was adapted from the evaluation form for printed instructional materials (WVSU-IQA-SOI-05-F01 from the Office of the Director of Instruction and Quality Assurance (DIQA) of WVSU. This evaluation form was utilized to evaluate the developed IM as the latter needs to be validated by experts for acceptability using the following criteria: objectives, physical aspects, activities, accuracy and up-to-datedness of information, and assessment.

2.5. Research procedure

Since this study adopted the IPO framework in the development of IM for ELE 202 structure of English following the development research design, the process was run through in detail as revealed in the explanations:

2.5.1. Input stage

The initial phase of this study is the gathering of data by conducting the instrument. A total of 39 students were randomly chosen to be the respondents of the study out of the 43-student population of the BSEd-1A section. These students underwent a 20-minute orientation as to the proceedings of the conduct of the questionnaire along with the protocols to be observed and followed. The conduct of the questionnaire for writing assessment and interview was done at the most convenient time for the students for a maximum of 90 minutes with a break at each session. They were properly oriented as well as carefully observed and meticulously supervised as to the nature and conduct of the activity. The respondents were given an hour to finish answering the questionnaire. Both the researcher and the subject instructor helped in facilitating the conduct of the questionnaire.

The primary consideration in this stage was the determination of learners’ needs based on error analysis and assessment of their writing skills. Analysis and evaluation of these errors were done through writing assessments. Common writing errors were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed.

The results of the study were statistically treated and analyzed using rank, frequency, mean, and standard deviation for descriptive statistics. Interpretation of the needs assessment results provided baseline

data that would determine the learning gaps to be used as inputs in the selection and design of appropriate IM. Meanwhile, the ELE 202 syllabus was reviewed as to its content coverage and outcomes-based teaching and learning strategies as addressed in the stipulations of CMO 74 and 75, s. 2017.

2.5.2. Process stage

After the conduct of data gathering in the input stage, the researcher studied and analyzed the respondents' common writing errors, looked into their level of speaking and writing skills, and listed down probable activities that would address the learning gaps while at the same time drafting the topics or lessons to be tackled in line with the course objectives and learning outcomes specifically mentioned and outlined in the syllabus. First in the presentation is the unit title with the stated general objectives or learning outcomes. This is followed by an introduction of what the unit is all about or the rationale of all the lessons proper. Upon presentation of each lesson, specific learning objectives are laid down for students to follow to guide them in their study. This is then followed by a motivating activity that serves to activate learners' schema. Afterward, a brief discussion of the lesson is presented, followed by three or more relevant tasks to perk up learners' interest in the topic while at the same time helping them develop their productive skills. There are other suggested activities mentioned in each lesson to further equip them with knowledge and skills. Here, every lesson is presented with tasks for multimodal learning. Individual, collaborative, and communicative exercises are given to ensure hands-on and meaningful experience. A paper-and-pencil test is then done to determine learners' level of understanding of the lessons discussed and the tasks presented. The final part of the lesson is the giving of assignments for learners' further study and in-depth understanding of the lesson.

Since the target material is a multimodal English IM, the planning of the instructional design was carried out using performance-based and metacognitive activities that are enriched with multimedia and multiliterate details of information, and following Merrill's first principles of instruction, these tasks were carefully selected and aligned with the course instructional objectives. The conceptualization of a multimodal English IM is carried out against the backdrop of Merrill's five prescriptive instructional principles that enhance the quality of instruction across all situations [22]. These principles have to do with task-centeredness, activation, demonstration, application, and integration.

The highlights of these principles were encapsulated in the blueprint of the instructional design, while as to the physical aspects, the outline, format, and layout of the instructional package were planned and sketched out using publication software such as Adobe InDesign and Photoshop. To explain further and in detail, the blueprint of the design of the multimodal English IM based on the first principles of instruction was executed through the introduction of the different sections of the course workbook, as:

- i) **Activation:** this is where activating prior knowledge occurs based on the learners' schema. It is the mind-opening part of the lesson that tries to capture the interest of the readers before going into the gist of the discussion. This is found in the 'let us do this' section where a motivating activity is presented before the lesson proper.
- ii) **Task-centeredness:** here, learners are guided through a presentation of essential information about the topic. This is found in the section that serves as a springboard for discussion and where they also find interest in doing the task and gathering tidbits of knowledge independently and/or collaboratively. This is captured and actualized in the 'read and think' and 'do you know?' sections.
- iii) **Application:** learners apply skills through procedural and supportive information found in the lesson and through a selection of relevant, sequential, and scaffolding tasks. This is generated in the section where they learn to engage in cognitive exercises and to understand the lesson within the bounds of multimodalities.
- iv) **Integration:** in this section, opportunities are provided for the learners to integrate what they have learned and explore new ways of using them. Here, learners undergo assessment or enrichment exercises.
- v) **Demonstration:** in the presentation of this principle, the learners perform skills (or part-tasks) through a provision of procedural and supportive information. The course workbook is located in the section where they are generally persuaded to exhibit their creativity and innovativeness in using technology and other learning tools. This is the part that says learning is knowing what one knows to know them fully. This is facilitated and realized in the 'going further' section.

Having realized these principles of instruction in the different sections of a multimodal English IM, the researcher saw to it that while such developed material is thought out to be interestingly modular as well as essentially interactive in the initial presentation of each lesson and during discussion proper, there has to be a reasonably relevant feedbacking of performance to measure the extent with which the learners have attained objectively the learning outcomes of the unit at the end part of the lesson. This way, the learners can determine their weaknesses and strengths by self-evaluating the efforts they have made and the tasks they have performed. This is revealed in the course workbook's 'your scoreboard' section.

2.5.3. Output stage

This stage's primary objective was to package the IM in a way that incorporates evaluators' comments and suggestions. The evaluation of a multimodal English teaching resource by a panel of specialists utilizing the evaluation questionnaire served as the stage's culmination. Descriptive statistics were used to examine and interpret the evaluation data to assess how acceptable the teaching material was. Figure 1 shows the cover and Figure 2 shows a sample page of the developed multimodal IM.

Figure 1. The cover design of ELE 202

The STRUCTURE of a LANGUAGE

Noticing Collocations

Directions: Find on the Internet an article on any topic that you like to talk about. Print it out and underline as many collocations as you can find. Use them in a sentence. (20 points)

Test Yourself

Directions: Circle the word that best fits the context of the sentence. (10 points)

1. The driver turned the car lights on at (twilight/throng).
2. The (consumer/customer) sells video games and video tapes.
3. When the show is over, please leave by the nearest (exit/gully).
4. In the morning, I (arose/descended) from my sleep and got ready for school.
5. After you receive a gift, it is (shameful/polite) to send a thank you note.
6. It took (freedom/courage) to tell Mr. Burke that I broke his window.
7. Diving into (shallow/blind) water is very risky.
8. An unwrapped sandwich will quickly become (tasteless/stale).
9. The mayor was known for his (chicanery/stinginess) over the years cheating the public out of millions.
10. Felix spent years trying to satisfy his (wanderlust/lasciviousness) in other countries.

Do You Know?

Collocations are groups of words that frequently occur together. Every language develops different collocations. When you are reading in English, it is very important to notice collocations and to learn them together with the individual words. You will gain fluency and improve comprehension if you are familiar with common collocations.

Which photo best represents your mood right now? Why would you say so?

Build up Output Skills: A Course Workbook 7

Figure 2. Sample page on how multimodality is integrated into the activities

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Common writing errors of freshman BSEd English major students

The common writing errors of freshman BSEd English major students are discussed in terms of the two types of writing errors: interlingual and intralingual, that is presented in Table 1. Among the 12 common interlingual errors, the seven interlingual errors that ranked the highest in frequency were obtained. The error with the highest frequency is the wrong use of tenses (rank=1, $f=105$). Other errors follow suit, in a particular order as: capitalization (rank=2, $f=36$), comma (rank=3, $f=34$), preposition (rank=4, $f=32$), noun (rank=5, $f=30$), article (rank=6, $f=21$), and full stop (rank=7, $f=14$). Data reveals that obviously, the freshman English major students are not meticulously keen about the proper and appropriate use of tenses in sentence construction, and more so in writing composition. Errors in capitalization, commas, prepositions, and noun numbers and omission, on the other hand, are found to have almost similar numbers of occurrence or frequency.

The results presented show that errors in the use of tenses are the most prevalent among the participants' written essay outputs; while the error of not using a full stop (i.e., using a comma between two complete sentences) is the least prevalent interlingual error. Errors in tenses may be linked to sentence-level errors that played a crucial role in student's essay scores [23], because tense errors tend to strongly affect sentence construction. These errors are also frequent among the categories of errors mentioned in previous research [24]–[26]. Research indicates that students often struggle with the correct use of verb tenses, leading

to inconsistencies in their writing [27]. Similarly, a study in 2022 also reported common errors in the use of articles [28]. In other forms of ELE, errors are also common in writing. For example, Malaysian tertiary students studying the English language tend to make mistakes in subject-verb agreement and verb tenses [29], which is also a similar result to the results of this study. Several factors contribute to errors in English writing, including first language interference, overgeneralization of English rules, and inadequate exposure to the target language [30]. Table 1 presents the results of the questionnaire on the common writing errors of freshman BSEd English major students. Meanwhile, given the 21 common intralingual errors, the seven highest in terms of frequency and ranks were obtained, as presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Common interlingual writing errors of freshman BSEd English major students

Classification of error	<i>F</i>	Rank
Tense	105	1
Capitalization	36	2
Comma	34	3
Preposition	32	4
Noun	30	5
Article	21	6
Full stop	14	7

Table 2. Common intralingual writing errors of first-year BSEd English major students

Classification of error	<i>F</i>	Rank
Unnecessary word	106	1
Punctuation	46	2
Run-on sentences	44	3
Word choice	41	4
Fragment	25	5
Pronoun (inappropriate use)	17	7
Pronoun antecedent agreement/pronoun shift intersentence	17	7
Spelling	17	7

The error with the highest frequency falls on the respondents' tendency to use unnecessary words (rank=1, $f=106$). These unnecessary words, or students' penchant for verbiage, redundancy, and use of unqualified repetitive words or ideas in writing can be associated with their poor vocabulary or their lack of it. Other errors follow suit, in particular order, as: punctuation (rank=2, $f=46$), run-on sentences (rank=3, $f=44$), word choice (rank=4, $f=41$), fragment (rank=5, $f=25$), pronoun (rank=7, $f=17$), pronoun-antecedent agreement/pronoun shift inter-sentence (rank=7, $f=17$), and spelling (rank=7, $f=17$).

In line with the results of the study as to the level of speaking and writing skills of the respondents, certain issues and concerns were raised to relate to and corroborate the common findings of other studies in error analysis: that having lexical understanding is vital to the goal of language proficiency, and that students' writing skills require a sufficient amount of vocabulary for effective enhancement. At this point, the study of Hossain *et al.* [23] on Filipino learners' ESL errors is justifiably relevant. Students need to be given more effective strategies on how to enlarge their vocabulary for academic survival. Likewise, teachers need to remind students of the importance of one's knowledge of errors in punctuation or mechanics in writing for effective and productive self-expression.

3.2. Development of multimodal instructional material for ELE 202 (structure of English)

ELE 202 (structure of English) is one of the subjects of the BSEd major in the English curriculum. It focuses on developing learners' ability to use the phonological, lexical, syntactic, and semantic structures of English in written and oral communication. It further equips them with skills in explaining the form, meaning, and use of various English language structures which are useful in their role as future facilitators of language teaching and learning. Generally, it aims to develop their intellectual competencies through a higher-level textual and visual comprehension as well as proficient and effective communication with realistic emphasis specifically on writing, speaking, and the use of new technologies [12]. In this paper, students' writing skills are examined throughout the entirety of the course ELE 202. The identified common writing errors were utilized for the next phase of the study: the development of the multimodal IM. The IM was developed using the IPO model following Merrill's first principles of instruction as instructional guidelines in lesson planning and outlining tasks as well as in the creation of IM [31].

To serve as inputs to the study, the researcher has performed error analysis to acquire baseline data on students' needs based on the assessment results of the level of writing skills of the first-year BSEd English major students. Gathered data were henceforth used to design IM based on the existing course outline and

syllabus that were used as a guiding framework and obtained from the campus and the university. Topics were likewise selected to suit students' needs based on CHED requirements in developing BSEd English major students' intellectual, oral, and written competencies.

3.3. Introducing multimodality in the instructional material

Based on the topics presented in the syllabus for the course ELE 202, the researcher integrated the concept of multimodality into the IM. First, he consulted the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) in line with the implementation of the curriculum in language education and probable activities to be included in the IM. The CEFR is an action-oriented guide in designing curricula and courses based on real-world communicative needs, shifting away from syllabuses through language structures. The CEFR aims to "promote proficiency perspective guided by 'can do' descriptors rather than a deficiency-perspective that focuses on what the learners have not yet acquired" [32].

The production activities suggested by the CEFR, along with other exercises gleaned and patterned after various activities mentioned in several multimodal references, served as examples to follow in accomplishing lesson objectives. The concept of multimodality is integrated into these activities as presented in semiotic resources such as visual images, gestures, movement, postures, sound, and other forms of media. There are three activities a learner may accomplish after a brief introduction to the lesson. The assessment exercise is not a multimodal activity since it focuses only on the measurement or determination of the learner's progress, particularly on the knowledge level. However, the tasks presented in each lesson are multimodal presentations of how writing and speaking competencies can be enhanced. The task that requires learners' motivation to do digital assignments through the use of technology (e.g. using the internet) is a good example of a multiliterate (or multimodal) activity necessitating multimedia know-how. Pictures on the pages are presented as semiotic resources to reveal learners' thoughts and emotions (i.e., another multimodal meaning-making representation) such that they engage learners to relate their previous experience (i.e., learners' schema) through the introduction of the visuals.

To elaborate further, these activities are presented based on the visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic (VARK) model of learning, which accounts for learners' different learning styles. The VARK model explains the fact that students learn in different ways—e.g., some learn by merely reading, others by looking at anybody demonstrating an act, which they then follow, while others watch the video and take notes thereafter [33].

3.4. The unique features of the instructional material

To create IM from a multimodal perspective, the researcher made sure that the following features are uniquely embedded in the workbook:

- i) Task-based orientation: the instructional manual contains at least three major tasks in each lesson for the learners to follow and accomplish. These are spiraling activities ranging from a simple recall of information to individual or collaborative multiliterate activities. They are meant to tap learners' potential to develop their speaking and writing competencies.
- ii) Minimalized discussion: as the instructional manual is conceived to be a supplementary tool intended to develop learner's speaking and writing skills, all topics are laid out in such a way that lessons are briefly summed up or reviewed, i.e., it is assumed that major textbooks are provided elsewhere by the course facilitator and learners are guided to work independently on the topics by doing research work and in-depth study of the lessons. This follows the principles of discovery learning following a constructivist view in the implementation of instruction.
- iii) Visually-enriched mode of interaction: visuals are considered to be semiotic resources that help captivate learners' interest to go on with the lessons and master the necessary output skills, similarly in the form of a picture talk, from which activity this multimodal instructional manual draws its inspiration. This idea follows the principles of the communicative approach in language learning.

With the features of a multimodal IM in mind, the researcher crafted the layout and the design of the prototype using the Adobe InDesign application, and with the comments, suggestions, and recommendations from the panel of technical and curriculum experts as well as those of English faculty evaluators, the said IM was created.

3.5. The evaluation of the multimodal English instructional material

To determine the level of acceptability of the developed IM, the researcher utilized the university's evaluation form for printed IM. This evaluation form was adapted to address questions in relation to the IM objectives, physical aspects, activities, accuracy and up-to-datedness of information, and assessment. Overall results indicated that, as far as the criteria such as objectives, physical aspects, activities, accuracy and up-to-datedness of information, and assessment are concerned, the multimodal IM was rated to be very

acceptable, conforming to academic standards and guidelines. Experts considered the said IM appropriately crafted in design and layout, rich in visual and linguistic resources along with its cohesive and dynamic activities that integrate multimedia tools and equipment, and saddled with hands-on performance tasks and measurable learning outcomes. Table 3 sums up the evaluative points of these criteria.

Table 3. The overall evaluation of the multimodal English IM

Evaluation criteria	SD	M	Description
1. Objectives	0.37	3.80	Very acceptable
2. Physical aspects	0.32	3.85	Very acceptable
3. Activities	0.18	3.90	Very acceptable
4. Accuracy and up-to-datedness of information	0.24	3.83	Very acceptable
5. Assessment	0.18	3.89	Very acceptable
Overall rating	0.26	3.85	Very acceptable

Note. n=7. Interpretation is based on the following scale/criteria: 1.00–1.50=barely acceptable; 1.51–2.50=moderately acceptable; 2.51–3.50=acceptable; 3.51–4.00=very acceptable.

The integration of multimodality in the production of IM in English is not an uncommon concept in the 21st-century trend of teaching, as it allows opportunities for multi-faceted learning and teaching. The aforementioned findings aligned with the research by Bacio and Sagge [34]–[36], emphasizing the necessity for IM to be appropriate for their intended users, based on acceptable objectives, content, activities, and assessment. This agreement was further reinforced by the findings of Embajador study [37], highlighting the appropriate use of instructional resources by educators to improve student learning.

4. CONCLUSION

The first-year BEd English major students' ability to write is mainly hampered by their lack of vocabulary to be able to express their ideas, thoughts, and feelings in writing, well and effectively. As much as their desire to develop a conversational skill is affected by hesitation and faulty utterances for want of vocabulary, all their efforts to organize their thoughts in writing were affected by various factors like verbiage, roundabout expressions, poor knowledge and mastery of the tenses, grammatical mistakes, and poor understanding of mechanics and punctuation. Fragmentary lines, unnecessary words, poor diction, and misspellings can be attributed to a poor development or buildup of vocabulary during their early years of education. Hence, eventually, they find a lot of difficulties in expressing themselves well within the four walls of the classroom.

This typical scenario in a classroom setting understandably requires extra consideration and careful examination of the current curriculum and instructional objectives of the institution. Students need more time and attention than ever before to master the skills necessary for them to survive in the 21st century. Perhaps, innovation in the field of instruction is too much for a prize to ask, but given the demands for high-end jobs and higher income, education needs to revisit its challenges beyond vision, mission, goals, and objectives. Thus, learners need to be globally competitive in the global market for them to survive in a fast-changing world.

Within this spectrum, the development and creation of a relevant and usable multimodal IM that is suited to the needs of the learners and aligned with the instructional objectives of the academe and the CHED mandate may be seen as an immediate and appropriate recourse to address the problem gaps on students' written and oral competencies. Working out an easy-to-understand, eye-catching text with graphic designs, illustrations, and vivid imagery while using multimedia tools and equipment and applying the principles of multiliteracy can be handy and efficient in carrying instructions toward skills enhancement, not to mention the series of collaborative and individual tasks to be followed according to students' pace of learning. The IM as a supplementary aid in the form of a workbook may facilitate the metacognitive performance of students who need help in skills upgrading through drills and exercises in the comfort of their time. The workbook is a self-instructional text that tackles language issues and topics on syntax, grammar, vocabulary, phonology, and semantics while simultaneously harnessing students' oral and written potential and capabilities based on the spiraling principle of instruction. The build-up output skills workbook is compliant with the requirements for printed educational materials. The exercises and tasks therein are meant to introduce learners to work collaboratively with a group and/or individually with a sense of self-reliance through skills enhancement based on both theory and practice.

The findings of this study are meant to contribute knowledge and insights to the field of research and extension work, learning and instruction, and future research. The output of this research (which is the multimodal IM) may be utilized for ELE, not only at the university level but also across various levels of

education. The material may also serve as a tool for instruction and the basis for any pedagogical undertakings for learners' self-enhancement so that both educators and curriculum experts may replicate, design, and develop IM tailored-fit for their own set of learners.

Lastly, the findings presented in this paper provide a unique perspective in looking into the curriculum of ELE in the Philippines. This may also encompass relevant issues and concerns in education in other countries whose first language is not English but use English as a medium of instruction in schools and universities and even in different industries and businesses. Examining the writing errors of high school and university students may help teachers provide appropriate and need-specific instructional techniques and strategies utilizing authentic and practicable resources. Eventually, this paper hopes to contribute to the holistic improvement of the writing skills of today's younger generation who will later on become the driving force for progress and positive change in their respective academic communities.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from West Visayas State University. Restrictions apply to the availability of these data, which were used under license for this study. Data are available https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Pet8QnHrzUoLKZUjzSAO3TCo6Ui11xuw?usp=drive_link with the permission of West Visayas State University.

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